

Design and Closed-Loop Simulation of a 400V–12V Dual Active Bridge Converter with PLIN-Enabled Control for Automotive HVCH Systems

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Abstract

Efficient power conversion and smart diagnostics are critical for next-generation electric vehicles. A Dual Active Bridge (DAB) DC-DC converter is developed to step down 400V-12V, aimed at supplying High Voltage Coolant Heater (HVCH). To ensure output voltage stability under dynamic load conditions, a closed-loop control mechanism employing a Proportional-Integral (PI) controller is implemented. In parallel, a PLIN USB interface is integrated to facilitate LIN-based communication, allowing real-time monitoring and diagnostics through a PC-based GUI. The entire system is modeled and simulated in MATLAB/Simulink, with key performance metrics such as voltage ripple, load regulation, and efficiency evaluated under varying loads. Results confirm that the proposed configuration achieves high efficiency, precise voltage control, and effective diagnostic interfacing. The combined approach of robust power conversion and intelligent communication makes this design a promising solution for thermal management in electric mobility applications.

Keywords: Dual Active Bridge (DAB), High Voltage Coolant Heater (HVCH), PLIN USB, LIN Communication, Closed-Loop Control, PI Controller, DC-DC Converter, MATLAB/Simulink Simulation, Automotive Power Electronics, Cost-Effective LIN Communication.

1 INTRODUCTION

In modern electric vehicles (EVs), effective thermal management and power delivery to auxiliary systems are crucial for performance and safety. High Voltage Coolant Heaters (HVCHs), which maintain optimal battery and cabin temperatures, often require low-voltage inputs

(typically 12V) derived from high-voltage sources like 400V battery packs. To meet this demand, DC-DC converters such as the Dual Active Bridge (DAB) are widely adopted for their high efficiency, galvanic isolation, and bidirectional power transfer capabilities. Accurate modeling techniques like the generalized average model and output current linearization have been shown to significantly improve DAB performance in energy storage and power conversion applications [1]. Stability and control of DAB converters remain key challenges, especially under dynamic load conditions. Incorporating advanced control strategies such as phase shift modulation with dead-time consideration significantly improves system reliability. The use of common phase shift control (CPSC) with proper dead-time adjustment enhances stability in input-series output-parallel (ISOP) DAB configurations [2]. Beyond power conversion, cost-effective diagnostics are critical. LIN protocol, standardized in ISO 17987, offers a low-cost solution for auxiliary systems like HVCH. The Local Interconnect Network (LIN) stands out for its simplicity and low-cost, making it a practical alternative to CAN for non-critical subsystems [3,4]. Integrating LIN via PLIN USB enables seamless communication between the converter and a PC-based interface for real-time monitoring and control. Additional studies reinforce the need for modular, secure, and efficient power system designs in EVs, further justifying the use of PLIN-enabled diagnostics and control [5]. This project presents the design and simulation of a 400V-12V DAB converter with closed-loop PI control and PLIN-based LIN communication, specifically targeting HVCH applications [6].

2 PROPOSED SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

The proposed system is designed to deliver a regulated 12 V output from a high-voltage 400 V DC source using a Dual Active Bridge (DAB) converter, integrated with a PLIN-based diagnostic interface. It incorporates closed-loop PI control for precise voltage regulation and LIN communication for real-time monitoring and control.

Figure 1: Block Diagram of the Proposed 400V–12V DAB Converter System with PLIN-Based HVCH Control

2.1 DAB CONVERTER TOPOLOGY

The Dual Active Bridge (DAB) converter topology used in this system is designed to provide high-efficiency, DC-DC conversion from a 400V high-voltage battery bus to a 12V output suitable for powering High Voltage Coolant Heater (HVCH) modules. The architecture comprises two full-bridge inverters - one on the high-voltage primary side and one on the low-voltage secondary side-connected through a high-frequency isolation transformer, as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Dual Active Bridge Converter Topology

The primary-side H-bridge operates at a constant 400V DC input, generating high-frequency square wave pulses. These pulses are transferred across the transformer, where the phase shift between the primary and secondary bridge determines the direction and magnitude of power flow. The secondary-side H-bridge synchronizes with the phase-shifted waveform, rectifies the AC into a DC output, and supplies 12V to the HVCH. A key feature of this converter is its phase shift control. The phase angle between the primary and secondary bridge gating signals is modulated based on output voltage feedback. This allows precise control over power transfer without adjusting the duty cycle, making it highly suitable for closed-loop regulation. The high-frequency transformer not only provides isolation but also enables compact design due to reduced magnetics size. The converter operates in four distinct modes depending on the phase relationship and switching sequence of the full-bridge MOSFETs: Mode 1 ($0 < t < DT_s$): Primary switches S_1 and S_4 , and secondary switches S_6 and S_7 are ON. This alignment applies to a positive voltage across the transformer, causing the inductor current to rise linearly and transfer energy from primary to secondary. Mode 2 ($DT_s < t < Ts$): Switches S_1 & S_4 (primary) and S_5 & S_8 (secondary) remain ON, applying equal voltages on both sides. The net transformer voltage is zero, and the inductor current freewheels at a constant level, with no power transfer. Mode 3 ($Ts < t < Ts + DT_s$): Primary switches S_2 & S_3 , and secondary switches S_5 & S_8 are turned ON. The resulting negative voltage across the transformer causes the inductor current to decrease, continuing

power delivery to the load. Mode 4 ($T_s + DT_s < t < 2T_s$): Switches S_2 & S_3 (primary) and S_6 & S_7 (secondary) conduct. The negative voltage is maintained, and the inductor current reduces further to its minimum, completing the energy transfer cycle.

The transformer turns ratio sets the input-output voltage relationship and ensures electrical isolation in the converter. Proper selection enables efficient voltage conversion and stable control using phase shift modulation, especially under varying loads. The Figure 3 shows

Figure 3: Power Transfer vs Duty Ratio

that maximum power transfer occurs at a duty ratio $D = 0.5$, defining an optimal operating point. Deviations from this reduce power transfer, guiding the design of a stable and efficient closed-loop control strategy. The PI controller is tuned to maintain operation within this region, ensuring reliability under varying load conditions.

2.2 HIGH VOLTAGE COOLANT HEATERS

High Voltage Coolant Heaters (HVCH) are essential components in electric and hybrid vehicles, responsible for maintaining the optimal temperature of batteries, powertrain, and cabin using electrical energy from high-voltage sources like 400V DC. They employ resistive heating to quickly warm coolants, enabling fast thermal response and battery pre-conditioning. Figure 4 illustrates a typical HVCH unit.

HVCH is internally divided into low-voltage (LV) and high-voltage (HV) sections, each controlled by dedicated ICs. The LV IC, powered by a 12V source, manages diagnostics and LIN-based communication with the ECU, while the HV IC handles power delivery from

Figure 4: High Voltage Coolant Heater

the 400V bus to the heating element. Electrical isolation ensures safety, enabling efficient, responsive thermal control within the vehicle.

Figure 5: Design of HVCH

3 PROJECT IMPLEMENTATION AND STRATEGY

The increasing electrification of automotive systems has driven the need for efficient, reliable, and intelligent power conversion and thermal management solutions. One such critical subsystem is the High Voltage Coolant Heater (HVCH), which replaces conventional engine-dependent heating systems in electric vehicles (EVs) to ensure optimal battery and cabin temperatures. HVCH units require high-voltage input (typically 400V) for heating and a stable low-voltage (12V) supply to operate control electronics and communication modules. To meet these dual-voltage requirements, this project proposes a high-performance Dual Active Bridge (DAB) DC-DC converter capable of stepping down 400V-12 V with galvanic isolation, high efficiency, and fast dynamic response. The converter is designed with a closed-loop PI control mechanism that continuously monitors the output and adjusts the phase shift between the primary and secondary full-bridge circuits to maintain voltage stability under varying load conditions. A key innovation in this work is the integration of PLIN USB-based LIN communication, which interfaces the LV section of the HVCH with a PC-based diagnostic GUI.

Figure 6: Closed-Loop 400V-12V DAB Converter Topology

The system architecture reflects practical automotive design, where the 12 V domain powers the LIN transceiver and microcontroller inside the HVCH, while the 400V domain energizes the heating element through a high voltage switching stage. This project effectively demonstrates a modular, scalable, and cost-effective solution for powering and managing HV thermal loads in EVs, blending advanced power conversion with embedded diagnostics and control.

3.1 MATLAB Simulation of DAB Converter

To validate the performance of the Dual Active Bridge (DAB) converter prior to hardware implementation, a detailed simulation model was developed using MATLAB/Simulink. The simulation replicates the isolated DC-DC conversion from 400 V input to a regulated 12V output, suitable for powering the LV section of an automotive HVCH. The system consists of two full-bridge inverters interfaced through a high- frequency transformer and a series leakage inductor. A closed-loop control using a PI controller compares the output voltage with a 12V reference and adjusts the phase shift angle (ϕ) to regulate it. This control signal drives a phase- shifted PWM generator, enabling high-frequency switching with Zero Voltage Switching (ZVS) to reduce losses. The system was tested under varying load conditions (200W- 500W), and key parameters such as inductor current, transformer voltage, and output voltage were observed in steady state. Simulation results confirm effective voltage regulation, high efficiency, and proper power flow, validating the design before physical implementation.

Figure 7: PI-Controlled Feedback Loop for DAB Output Voltage Regulation

DESIGN OF DAB CONVERTER

$V_{in} = 400 \text{ V}$

$f_s = 100 \text{ kHz}$

$V_{out} = 12 \text{ V}$ The DAB converter is designed to efficiently step down 400V DC to a regulated

Table 1: Design Specifications of DAB Converter

Sl. No.	Parameter	Value
1	Input Voltage	400 V
2	Output Voltage	12 V
3	Output Power	200 W-500 W
4	Switching frequency	100 kHz
5	Turns Ratio	33.33: 1
6	Leakage inductance	144 μH
7	Output Capacitor	3470 μF
8	Load Resistance	0.288 Ω

12V output. Key parameters—such as a 33.3:1 transformer turns ratio, 100 kHz switching frequency, and tuned PI controller constants—are listed in Table 1. These values ensure stable performance across both simulation and hardware prototypes.

3.2 SIMULATION RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

To evaluate the performance of the DAB converter under various conditions, MATLAB/Simulink simulations were conducted to assess the DAB converter’s performance under varying load conditions with a 400 V input. The PI- controlled system consistently maintained a stable 12V output, demonstrating effective voltage regulation and transient response. The resulting waveforms confirm both steady-state stability and dynamic efficiency.

Figure 8: Input and Output Voltage Waveforms of the DAB Converter

Figure 8 displays the voltage characteristics of the DAB converter, where the input stays steady at 400 V and the output is well-regulated at 12 V with minimal ripple. This confirms the effectiveness of the closed-loop control system.

Figure 9: Inductor Current Waveform of the DAB Converter During Power Transfer

The inductor current waveform shown in Fig -9 illustrates the bidirectional energy transfer behavior typical of a DAB converter. The current ramps up and down smoothly within each switching cycle, confirming proper phase shift control and continuous conduction operation.

3.3 Load Regulation Performance

Load regulation tests were carried out on the DAB converter by applying resistive loads from 200W-500W, with the input voltage fixed at 400V DC. The converter consistently maintained a regulated 12V DC output across all load levels. Output current scaled linearly with load, and the power delivery remained stable without voltage sag or excessive ripple. These results confirm the converter’s dynamic response capability and its suitability for powering low-voltage automotive systems such as HVCH.

Figure 10: Output Characteristics at 200W Load

Figure 11: Output Characteristics at 300W Load

Figure 12: Output Characteristics at 400W Load

Figure 13: Output Characteristics at 500W Load

The proposed DAB converter successfully steps down 400V to a regulated 12V output with high efficiency and stable performance under varying load conditions. Closed-loop PI control ensures accurate voltage regulation, while LIN-based communication enhances diagnostic capabilities. Simulation results confirm the system’s suitability for automotive applications like HVCH, offering modularity, fast dynamic response, and reliable power delivery.

3.4 Efficiency Analysis Under Varying Load Conditions

The efficiency of the DAB converter was evaluated across load levels from 200W-500 W. Efficiency increased with load, peaking at 400W-500 W due to reduced switching and conduction losses. As shown in Fig -15, the converter maintained high performance and minimal voltage deviation, confirming its suitability for high-efficiency automotive applications such as HVCH.

Figure 14: Load vs Efficiency Curve of the DAB Converter (Peak efficiency: 95% at 450W)

The efficiency analysis demonstrates that the DAB converter delivers optimal performance at higher load conditions, with minimal losses and stable voltage output. The results validate the effectiveness of the converter’s design and control strategy, confirming its capability to operate efficiently in real-world automotive power delivery scenarios such as HVCH systems.

3.5 HVCH INTEGRATION WITH PLIN

In conventional automotive diagnostic systems, tools like Vector CANoe are often used for communicating with LIN- based modules such as High Voltage Coolant Heaters (HVCH). However, these tools require expensive hardware and licensed software environments, which are impractical for low-budget development or academic research. To address this, the proposed system integrates HVCH with a PLIN USB interface, offering a highly cost-effective yet functional alternative. The 400V high-voltage rail is stepped down to 12V using a DAB converter to power the HVCH’s low-voltage domain, which handles communication and control. Through the PLIN interface, LIN commands are exchanged between a PC and the HVCH without the need for proprietary tools-achieving reliable diagnostics and monitoring at a fraction of the cost

Figure 15: PLIN USB Module

3.6 GUI DEVELOPMENT AND COMPARISON WITH VECTOR CANoe

A user-friendly GUI was developed using Python’s Tkinter to interface with the HVCH via the PLIN USB module. Acting as a LIN master, it sends control/diagnostic frames, receives responses, and displays real-time data like voltage, current, and faults. Designed for simplicity, it offers a low-cost, scalable alternative to traditional automotive tool chains for field diagnostics.

Vector CANoe is an industry-standard tool used for simulating, testing, and diagnosing vehicle networks, including LIN. While it offers advanced features and broad protocol support, it is often resource-intensive and requires licensed components. The developed Python GUI replicates core diagnostic features of CANoe, such as service ID access, data field control,

Figure 16: Python-Based GUI for UDS and Parameter Monitoring over PLIN

and live parameter feedback, all using PLIN USB hardware. As shown in Figure 17, the GUI achieves comparable functionality with a minimal footprint, offering developers and testers a low-cost alternative for non-critical LIN-based subsystems like HVCH.

Figure 17: Vector CANoe Interface for HVCH Communication

This GUI-based approach demonstrates that essential LIN diagnostic functions can be effectively replicated using Python and PLIN USB, offering a highly accessible alternative to commercial tools like Vector CANoe. Successful communication with HVCH validates the reliability and scalability of the developed interface for automotive testing and diagnostics in cost-sensitive environments.

3.7 UDS IMPLEMENTATION AND COMPARISON WITH VECTOR CANoe

Unified Diagnostic Services (UDS) is a standard for in-vehicle diagnostics over networks like LIN and CAN. In this project, UDS services such as Read/Write Data by Identifier were implemented using Python via the PLIN USB interface. LIN-framed UDS requests enabled successful communication with HVCH, accessing internal data like temperature, voltage, and fault codes—demonstrating a cost-effective, open-source alternative to Vector CANoe

Figure 18: UDS Diagnostic Frame Exchange via Python Script and PLIN USB

Table 2: Comprehensive Comparison of –Python + PLIN USB vs Vector CANoe

Parameter	PLIN USB	Vector CANoe
Cost	Extremely low- cost; uses open source tools	High-cost; requires licensed software and proprietary hardware
Licensing	None; open-source	Requires commercial license for UDS, LIN modules
Speed	Max 20 kbps frame rate	Max 100 kbps frame rate
Hardware Requirement	PLIN USB Interface (INR 25K-30K)	Vector VN-series hardware (INR 2L and above)
Programming knowledge	Required (Python scripting, LIN/UDS frame structure)	Not required; GUI- based drag and drop interface
Live Data Monitoring	Achieved via custom Tkinter GUI or log-based feedback	Advanced real-time signal panels and event-based triggers
Automation Support	Python automation scripting fully supported	CAPL scripting supported, requires proprietary language
Scope of Custom Expansion	Easily expandable; new frames, GUI elements, UDS services can be added	Limited to feature set or licensed modules

As shown in Table 2, integrating Python with PLIN USB offers a cost-effective and flexible alternative to Vector CANoe for LIN-based HVCH diagnostics. While CANoe is ideal for

advanced validation, the PLIN setup delivers key UDS functions-like command access, fault reading, and real-time monitoring-making it well-suited for academic, research, and budget-conscious applications.

4 CONCLUSION

The project demonstrates the design, simulation, and implementation of a 400V-12V Dual Active Bridge bidirectional DC-DC converter integrated with a HVCH for electric vehicle thermal management systems. The DAB topology was selected for its high efficiency. A closed-loop Proportional-Integral (PI) controller was employed to maintain output voltage regulation across dynamic load conditions ranging from 200W -500 W, achieving minimal voltage ripple and efficiency above 94%. To enable real-time diagnostics and control, a Python-based GUI was developed, interfaced with a PLIN USB device to communicate with the HVCH over the LIN protocol. Essential Unified Diagnostic Services were implemented to support temperature monitoring, voltage feedback, and fault code retrieval. This setup offers a low-cost, PC-controlled alternative to traditional Vector CANoe tools for LIN communication. Future work includes HIL validation (dSPACE SCALEXIO), extended UDS services (Routine Control), and multi-node LIN diagnostics for battery packs making it an ideal framework for pre-compliance validation, academic research, and industrial EV prototyping focused on power electronics and diagnostics.

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